

THE ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TRANSPORT GEOGRAPHY OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article aims to investigate the notion of the transport geography and its development aspects. In particular, the research presents the investigation of the transport geography of Karakalpakstan.

Geography of transport, a branch of economic geography that studies the territorial distribution of transport and transportation, its patterns, conditions and features of the development of transport as part of the territorial and economic complexes of countries and regions in conjunction with the distribution of natural conditions and resources, population and economic sectors. It reflects important features of transport as a branch of production: [3.12-15].

- a) a special form of using elements of the natural environment as natural routes of communication or the basis for artificial routes of communication;
- b) basically a linear type of distribution of transport, profoundly different from the prevailing types of distribution of industry (point) and agriculture (areal);
- c) the universality of technical and economic ties with other branches of the economy;
- d) the role of transport as one of the material foundations of the territorial and geographical division of labor;
- e) specific division into types (land, water, air transport) in contrast to the sectoral division typical for industry and agriculture;
- f) differences between modes of transport associated with the use of different natural and artificial means of communication;
- g) the specific nature of pricing (tariffs, freights), which affects the location of the entire economy, etc.[4.47-55].

The transport industry of the capitalist world, along with other problems, studies the influence on transport of the spontaneous and antagonistic distribution of the economy, economic crises, and the competitive struggle between the monopolies that control various types of transport; the influence of various forms of economic enslavement (colonialism and neo-colonialism), etc.[1.243-245].

At present, the state of the transport system and its development are of great importance for the economy, production potential, national security of the country as a whole

and its regions in particular. Along with and in close connection with energy, communications, education and healthcare, and other infrastructure sectors, transport provides normal conditions for human life, the functioning of public institutions and the production and consumption of material goods.[5.58-62]. Transport connects cities and countries, providing foreign economic interaction.

The transport system, or rather the degree of its development, plays an important role in choosing a rational location for enterprises, forming logistics chains, etc. Therefore, at present, even one very small project concerning the resettlement of the population or the formation of an industrial center is not accepted without elaborating issues related to transport links, and, consequently, without preliminary research and design and survey development.

The elements of the transport system are, first of all, the diversity of all ways, that is: railways and roads, air and waterways (river and sea), pipeline transport. All these paths are used for the movement of vehicles [2.94-98]. . A road is a transport infrastructure object used for the movement of vehicles. The road includes land plots within the boundaries of the right of way and structural elements located on them or under them (roadbed, pavement and similar elements). In addition, this includes road structures that are a technological part of the road, such as protective road structures, artificial road structures, production facilities, elements of the road arrangement.

Railway transport moves along special railway tracks and is divided into freight (covered wagons, platforms, gondola cars, tanks, refrigerators, others (cement carriers, grain carriers, mineral carriers, fitting platforms) and long-distance passenger and commuter trains [1]. Passenger transportation in trains long-distance transportation includes transportation in local traffic (carriage of passengers carried out within the same railway) and direct traffic (carriage of passengers carried out within two or more roads on a single ticket).

The main goal in the formation of the transport system is to create a transport balance of the industry, within which it is necessary to clearly outline the specific contribution of each specific mode of transport to the achievement of the goal of the region's transport system, which will not allow individual modes of transport to develop spontaneously and uncontrollably, and in the future will not give rise to a monopolist in the freight market. or passenger traffic. The existing transport system should provide competitive transport services that fully meet the needs of society in passenger and freight traffic.

The formation of the transport system of the region is influenced by a number of factors, the main of which are:

- the vastness of the territory of the region;
- population and concentration of places of resettlement;
- demographic level of the population by municipalities of the region;
- uneven distribution of raw materials and energy resources in the region;
- location of industrial centers;
- the number of products produced in the region;
- intensity of development of branches of material production;
- a historically established network of means of communication [5].

In this way, the factors influencing the development of the transport system (single transport space) are geopolitical, demographic, economic, resource and geographical. These factors are taken into account when planning strategies for the development of the industry, when developing plans for the development of transport systems, etc. Underestimation of any of the factors is fraught with problems in any part of the infrastructure, with the subsequent reflection of this problem in the industry as a whole.

In this way, the transport system is an open, complex, multicomponent system that connects all types of transport, the purpose of which is to increase transport accessibility while minimizing costs. Its development is due to a large number of factors, primarily demographic, resource, economic, etc.

The geographical transport of Karakalpakstan is important for the country's development on economic and social branch. The territory of Karakalpakstan in transport system is given in the following figure. [6].

The geography of transport system of Karakalpakstan

The transport system of Karakalpakstan consists of autotransportation roads, railway station and airlines.

Roads (length km.)

Nukus-Beruni-145.2 km.

Nukus-Turtkul-172.1 km.

Nukus-Muynak city - 213.2 km.

Nukus city Urgench-192.0 km.

Nukus-Bukhara-550.2 km.

Nukus city Navoi-657.5 km.

Nukus city - Karshi city - 734.5 km.

Nukus-Samarkand-821.9 km.

Nukus-Tashkent-1155.7 km.

Railways (length km.)

Nukus – station Oasis of the Republic of Kazakhstan – 459 km.

Nukus city – Karakalpakstan station – 439 km.

Nukus city Kungrad -131 km.

Nukus city – Khodjeyli city – 45 km.

Nukus city - Turtkul city - 166 km.

Nukus – Miskin Station – 196 km.

Nukus city Navoi-697 km

Nukus-Samarkand-853 km.

Nukus-Tashkent-1 190 km.

Air (directions of flights.)

Nukus city - Tashkent city

Nukus - Moscow

Muynak-Nukus city

The direction is the development of road and transport infrastructure, in particular, the creation of the railway line Chimbay - Takhtakopir - Kazakdarya - Ustyurt (railway Kungrad - Beyneu). Representatives of the Karakalpak branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan made a great contribution to the study of this direction.

This opens up the possibility of mining and transporting mineral resources such as marl, glauconite, bentonite, silicon, mirabilite, ilmenite in Beltau, Kuskhanatau, Porlytau, Akkala and Krantau, successfully develop industry and service enterprises, create jobs. This will make it possible to form a unified transport infrastructure in the Muynak region (connects the city of Muynak and the village of Kazakdarya), develop the fishing industry in the region and eco-tourism in the biological zones of the Amu Darya and Lake Sudochie.

Conclusion. The geography transportation system is important to the industry of the republic of Karakalpakstan. The main transportation systems are road transportation system, railway and airlines. The length of road transportation systems is differ from region to another region. The result of the research depicts that the geography of transport is not only rich in depth but also important in economics.

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